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Coming of age: Scottish new towns in the 21st century

Introduction: The Scottish initiative

Planning throughout the 20th century was an important element in Scotland's political culture. Scottish burghs, founded by charter from the 12th century onwards, had historic importance in the national constitution. Many of them were planned towns and all were guardians of their civic responsibilities and civic dignity. When, in 1903, Andrew Carnegie presented his home town with a gift of two and a half-million dollars, to bring into the lives of the toiling masses of Dunfermline more of sweetness and light, the reaction of the city fathers was to commission a survey and plan from Patrick Geddes and subsequently to establish a planning section in the burgh surveyor's department.

By 1900 the environmental and social problems that beset central Scotland, dependent on coal, steel and heavy engineering, were obvious. Aggravated by economic depression, housing and industrial reconstruction demanded massive investment by public agencies and the consensual view of planning, shared by the major political parties, was pursued by the devolved Scottish Office after its move to Edinburgh in 1939. The wartime Secretary of State, Tom Johnston, inspired by the example of the Tennessee Valley Authority, proposed regeneration of the Highlands by a hydro-electric authority which commenced immediately after the second World War, and set up regional planning teams to examine the problems of central Scotland.

The Clyde Valley Regional Plan

The planning team directed by Patrick Abercrombie and Robert Matthew reported in 1946. The problems of west central Scotland were concentrated

in Glasgow and the congested coal-mining areas to its south. The region contained over one-third of Scotland's population, with 22% in Glasgow alone.

The major concerns of the plan were to secure the containment of Glasgow's growth and dispersal of its population, and reconstruction of the region as an economic whole. The prescription included imposing a green belt around Glasgow and its surrounding towns to prevent merging and to preserve high amenity open land, to establish new towns and to expand some existing settlements as dispersal and growth points. Apart from green belt requirements, criteria for possible new town sites were strict, avoiding land liable to subsidence due to coal mining, and minimising use of high-quality agricultural land. A negative building map revealed four possible new town sites, at East Kilbride, to the south of Glasgow; two alternative sites near Renfrew to the west, and Cumbernauld, to the north-east.

These proposals were at first bitterly opposed by Glasgow. The proposed green belt included some 5,400 hectares of land within the city boundaries on which the council proposed to build. A plan by the city engineer claimed that the existing population could be rehoused, mainly in low-rise tenements at high density, and a powerful faction was intent on retaining the magic million population of the second city.

Within a few weeks of the Clyde Valley plan's publication the government commenced implementation of the decentralisation strategy and the designation of East Kilbride as a new town, to be managed by an appointed development corporation, forced confrontation with Glasgow. At a public enquiry the assumptions of the second city plan were refuted and designation was confirmed. East Kilbride was followed by Scotland's second new town, Glenrothes, a growth point in Fife, which, though far from the Clyde valley, would attract population from the declining coal mining areas south of Glasgow.

Development at East Kilbride began in June 1948, and despite continued opposition from Glasgow the first new town proved a great success. Glasgow residents began to apply for houses before any were built and within five years a modern industrial base was established, including the principal government engineering research establishment and Rolls-Royce aero engines division.

Cumbernauld, seven years later, represented a second generation of British new towns. Based on an existing community of 3,000 its location, 24 km from Glasgow centre, was an important node in the national road network. Cumbernauld conformed to the dispersal policy of the Clyde Valley plan, by then accepted by Glasgow, but was also seen as a

potential growth point to attract industrial and commercial development in central Scotland. Subsequent policy emphasised the >growth point= strategy in locating the fourth and fifth new towns at Livingston, 20 km west of Edinburgh, in 1962 and at Irvine, on the Ayrshire coast, in 1966. Irvine represented a break from previous location policy by expanding a well-established seaport town with a population of 34,500 at the time of designation. After 20 years of developing planning policy the five new towns, rather than clustering around the Glasgow conurbation, formed a chain through Scotland=s central belt.

Cumbernauld

As it is impossible here to discuss the character and fortunes of all five towns we will now concentrate on Cumbernauld, designated in 1955 to accommodate a self-contained town for 50,000 people.

The chief architect and planner Hugh Wilson=s approach represented a reaction to the >neighbourhood= principle adopted at East Kilbride and Glenrothes. Wilson wanted a compact urban area seeing zoning also as a negative approach: he had >no objection, for instance, to the placing of suitable industrial buildings .. to produce a more lively atmosphere in the town=; traffic should be segregated and parking problems called for fresh study. The master plan should not be specific but a brief to guide development.

We have an opportunity to design a cellular town, the houses within walking distance of the centre, with planting used as an integral part of the development and with levels that can be exploited to provide interest in the grouping of buildings. My office will be organised on a group basis with planners, architects, landscape architects and engineers working side by side= (Wilson, 1957, quoted by Lyddon).

In this ground-breaking approach lay the successes of Cumbernauld, its international fame and also some of its subsequent problems.

The principal objectives of the Cumbernauld plan were; circulation designed for 100% car ownership with separate road and footpath systems, housing to be largely in 1 and 2-storey cottages, with gardens for shelter and privacy and concentration of principal shopping, services and administration in a town centre with local shops, meeting rooms and small industrial units in residential areas.

Not only did the planning principles break the mould of earlier new towns; they were to be applied on a particularly challenging site, centred on a hilltop ridge on the watershed of central Scotland with valleys to north and south. The designated area was small and not all of it was buildable. The north-

facing slope was particularly steep, the south side more gentle.

Firm planning proposals evolved between 1958 and 1962 but initial development began at once. Glasgow was pressing for housing and an industrial site for up to 4000 employees had been allocated before the development corporation was set up. Wilson=s multi-disciplinary design teams were engaged on the three stated problems; high-density low-rise housing on sloping sites within strict cost limits, the hilltop town centre and the segregated road and footpath systems. The integration of those three elements, designed and refined as the town was being built, was the achievement of Cumbernauld. By 1967, after ten years, 5600 houses had been built and 6102 jobs provided. The achievement was recognised by the RS Reynolds Memorial Award, gained in competition with Vallingby, Stockholm and Tapiola in Finland, the jury commenting,

>... The town, though only partly complete, has already a real sense of community and place endearing it to both residents and visitors... The architects have achieved townscape on a shoestring ... effective urban design has been gained at moderate cost with a limited palette .. the dreams of the 1920s and 1930s are being built on a hill near Glasgow.=

The Town Centre

Within the integrated urban development of Cumbernauld the town centre attracted most acclaim: to many observers it was the image of the town, to many users it proved a disappointment and to all involved in its development and management an endless source of new problems.

The character of the town centre was inherent in Wilson=s concept of Cumbernauld as a compact development with most of the town=s commercial, social and administrative facilities concentrated in one central complex, accessible by footways from the residential areas, by private car and by public transport with complete separation of vehicles and pedestrians.

In the 1950s the multi-outlet shopping mall was almost unknown in Europe. Important precedents were Ralph Erskine=s shopping centre at Luleå in northern Sweden and his imaginative schemes for enclosed urban developments in arctic cities. And in 1956 a series of advertisements by Pilkington Brothers, glass manufacturers, described a >High Market= project, a hilltop megastructure near Dudley, in the English west midlands, to serve regional shopping and recreational needs.

Like the road system, the town centre programme was researched from basic principles. A team from Glasgow University and corporation staff sought a

more reliable measure of retail requirements than a crude estimate of numbers of shops. From available statistics, sales were assessed for the likely local and catchment area populations, and floor area requirements for each trade group, numbers of employees in retail and related activities and likely car parking requirements were calculated. At the same time commercial reactions were sought and a firm of estate surveyors engaged as consultants and subsequently as letting agents. It was realised that both leasing arrangements and building structure should be flexible and allow for changing and unforeseen patterns of retail distribution to avoid obsolescence.

The design revealed in 1962, and presented with almost evangelical fervour by the team leader, Geoffrey Copcutt was heroic; an eight-level structure containing shops, housing, offices, restaurants, pubs, theatre, library, hotel and local government, more than one kilometre in length when completed, would crown the hilltop, straddling a dual-carriageway central way.

Such a leviathan could not be built at once and the decision to begin phase I in 1963, when the new town was barely five years old, was itself a heroic act of faith. There had been debate whether the first phase should be a complete deck, or a >slice= through the megastructure. The decision to construct a slice, though later seeming a recipe for near-disaster, forged the image of Cumbernauld and secured the remarkable skyline which in some views seems a man-made extension of the hill-top.

Phase I, completed in 1968, comprised two principal elements, the main commercial, administrative and housing block, a tiered 7-storey agglomeration crowned by a row of penthouses, and a spur to the north, bridging the central way. Phase II, above and adjoining the northern spur, comprised a single 3-storey block of offices and shops with car parking below. Since completion of phase II in 1972 these buildings have formed the core of the town centre, to which other components were added and some removed in successive phases, the rooftop penthouses being converted to offices in 1985.

The centre=s fortunes have risen and fallen over the years and decommissioning in 1996 found it in rather a sorry state. The outgoing development corporation succeeded however in appointing developers to undertake a, 75 million modernisation and extension programme to create more than 11,000 sq m of new shopping. Extension to the south will be achieved by demolishing the lower southern section of phase I to form a new entrance area with shopping malls extending towards a new department store to the west. Meanwhile modernisation of the older shopping levels is well advanced though

plans to restore the penthouse level to housing have been impeded by fire regulations.

The new buildings will not exceed two storeys, will embrace a town square, lacking in Cumbernauld, and provide entrance areas more welcoming than the present, sometimes puzzling, tunnels and ramps. The through route of the central way will be lost - it never achieved its intended expression anyway because of failure to complete the western sector - but a new bus station under the building will retain the principle of direct, sheltered access. Gone is integral car parking, attempted below the shopping areas in phases I to III and on a supermarket roof in phase IV but too costly and inflexible for modern shopping developments. The heroic hill-top profile will survive as a solid core contrasting with the fussy decor of a new shopping mall. We must hope that the town centre will remain both commercially viable and a recognisable memorial to the designers of Cumbernauld, responding, in Hugh Wilson=s words, to the >changing conditions and demands= of the 21st century.

“Through-composed” planning

An expression from opera might explain Cumbernauld=s approach to layout, enabled by the development corporation=s status as, in effect, sole landowner. Developers and designers of individual elements, such as churches and schools, were not presented with sites defined by pegs in the ground but worked with the town design team to relate their buildings to surrounding development before site boundaries, access arrangements and intermediate planting were fixed. The success of this approach to townscape, the spaces between being as important as the buildings themselves, can be seen still by the visitor walking through Cumbernauld. Ideally boundaries need no physical reinforcement; public and private spaces should be apparent, but that principle has not everywhere survived fragmentation of ownership and concerns with >security=. For example, Kildrum primary school (1960), by Gillespie Kidd & Coia is now separated by 2m high palisade fencing from the adjoining sheltered playing field.

Central area housing

The first housing areas, in an elongated >doughnut= layout round the hilltop, were high-density, mainly family houses with private gardens, planned on modified >Radburn= principles. Historically important, they signalled in Scotland a departure from open-space post-war housing layouts to denser, more complex, patterns strongly influenced by Scandinavian examples. Though designed for collective ownership and management, most areas have survived the trend to owner-occupation. But after 40

years low-cost housing needs, at least, extensive servicing, and Carbrain, south of the town centre, is by general agreement, due for renewal and deck-access flats there have already been demolished. The remaining low-rise housing, though ingenious in design and cherished by some of its occupants, is not something that conservationists would die for, but it is important in its location on the southern approach to the town centre; for visitors arriving by train Carbrain is the entrance to Cumbernauld.

Redevelopment at Carbrain will be overseen by a partnership of housing agencies and a residents= organisation, and a development brief, intended to retain the high-density, low-rise character of the hilltop housing areas is being prepared. But no part of Cumbernauld has any statutory protection and the official valuers, obliged to apply a monetary test on disposal of publicly-owned assets, might favour the standard pattern of speculative development prevalent to the north of the town.

The future of Cumbernauld

Cumbernauld is not completely at the mercy of market forces; the district planning department and concerned residents= organisations are aware of the value of their legacy, but commercial interest is hard to resist. A study by the Conservation Unit of Edinburgh College of Art in 1998, while identifying the values of Cumbernauld as a unique planned environment and, while recognising the difficulties of protection, recommended that the central housing areas and the town centre should be designated as a conservation area of outstanding status and that application should be made to UNESCO for Cumbernauld to be included in the World Heritage List.

World Heritage List nomination was considered by DOCOMOMO Scotland at the time of the Registers Committee=s WHL report. Guidelines require local protection of the monument and assurance of its future maintenance, neither of which was in place for the town centre. The hilltop housing conservation area could and should be supported. Conservation area submissions normally adopt a street by street approach. At Cumbernauld quality is in the integrity of the whole and even consideration by housing areas must be resisted. The area would be large, but not so large as Edinburgh=s 18th century New Town.

Conclusion: the Scottish new towns

In 1995 East Kilbride was said to be the sixth largest town in Scotland, Cumbernauld the ninth, and all five new towns must rank among the largest twelve or so. Their achievements are undeniable; Glenrothes, Irvine and Livingston are local administrative capitals, virtually county towns; East Kilbride an industrial centre of international status; Cumbernauld, the most famous,

curiously something of a Cinde-rella, still attracting hi-tech industrial investment, still, as house sales confirm, a desirable place to live but subordinate to Motherwell, the established centre of North Lanarkshire.

The urban design characteristics of [Cumbernauld=s] early phases sound like a shopping list of desiderata for the twenty-first-century urban periphery: compact planning and split level flexibility, ... private gardens, spatial openness, ... sharp perimeter definition of the urban area, ... respect for the *genius loci* and immediacy of contact with nature, through a predominately grey-and-white built image and flowing, forest-like landscaping. (Gleninning & Page, 1999)

That initial rigour, though relaxed in Cumbernauld=s later phases, was reflected in different ways in the other four new towns. Their continued attraction to private housing developers, now at commercial land values, and the identification of Livingston, by an academic study in 1997, as the second most desirable town to live in Britain support that assessment.

Yet living in one of the new towns can still produce reactions of amused surprise. They are not yet realised, culturally or historically, as even are Helensburgh or Port Glasgow, both planned creations of the last two centuries. More serious has been their hasty decommissioning and the dispersal of professional and administrative expertise, the value of which seemed to be accepted in directing the East Kilbride team to support Glasgow urban renewal in the 1970s.

The Adam Smith Institute, a right-wing think-tank not usually regarded as a friend of planning, discussing the future of the Scottish new towns in 1988, recognised their special identity and commercial success, praising particularly the high quality and professionalism of their staff, concluding;

The new towns stand ready to move to the next stage of their evolution. It is possible to see them as a completely new type of social organization, and to take the opportunity to introduce changes which could serve as models for the rest of Scotland, and to devise arrangements more suited to the special character of the new towns, It could be that the achievements of the new towns could thus be spread more widely than the boundaries within which they have so far taken place.

While suspecting the dirigist style of the development corporations we might see them as counterparts of the early Scottish burghs with their elitist feudal structure. East Kilbride was briefly constituted as a burgh, beginning to transfer centralist management to local democratic control. The tradition of small-town management, developing the local civic dimension, might have retained and enhanced the values of the new towns more securely than by

their absorption into large district authorities and underlined their important role, not only as economic growth points, but as exemplars for a structured development of central Scotland.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abercrombie, Sir Patrick & Matthew, Robert M (1949) *The Clyde Valley regional plan*, Edinburgh.
- Adam Smith Institute (1988) *Livingston plc, I presume?*, London.
- Banham, Reyner (1976) *Megastructure*, London.
- City of Glasgow Corporation (1947) *First and second planning reports*, 2nd edition, Glasgow.
- Cowling, David (1997) *An essay for today; the Scottish new towns 1947 to 1997*, Edinburgh.
- Cumbernauld New Town Development Corporation (1962) *Cumbernauld New Town Planning Proposals - Second Revision*, Cumbernauld.
- Cumbernauld New Town Development Corporation (1965) *Technical brochure*, Cumbernauld.
- Cumbernauld New Town Development Corporation (1996) *Annual Report 1995*, Cumbernauld.
- Glendinning, Miles (1996) >Megastructure and *genius loci*: the architecture of Cumbernauld new town= *Proceedings: Fourth DOCOMOMO International Conference*, Bratislava, pp 123-127.
- Glendinning, Miles & Page, David (1999) *Clone city*, Edinburgh.
- Lyddon, Derek (1994) *New town record: Cumbernauld*, unpublished ms.

Opher, Philip & Bird, Clinton (1980) *Cumbernauld, Irvine, East Kilbride: an illustrated guide*, Oxford.

Secretary of State for Scotland (1947) *New Town (East Kilbride) Designation Order 1946*, Edinburgh.

PERIODICALS

Architectural Design; May 1963, pp 206-225.

CD-ROM

The Planning Exchange (1997) *The new towns record: 1956-1996*, Glasgow.

⁸ David Whitham, October 2000

KEYWORDS

new towns in regional context, history and significance of Cumbernauld; dilemmas of conservation and planning for change; new towns as exemplars for future development.

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Fig. 1 – Central Scotland: Map showing the five Scottish New Towns.

Fig. 2 – Cumbernauld New Town: air view from east, 1967. Town Centre Phase 1 almost completed; Phase 2 under construction. In background: point blocks and row housing in Seafar and Ravenswood areas. (Cumbernauld New Town Development Corporation)

Fig. 3 – Cumbernauld Town Centre in 1980. The Technical College is on the left. (Philip Opher)

Fig. 4 – Cumbernauld New Town: split-level housing on a north-facing slope in Seafar. (Cumbernauld New Town Development Corporation)

Fig. 5 – Irvine New Town: The Bridgegate development in the historic burgh centre. (Philip Opher) & David Whitham, October 2000